

Software patterns and architectural decisions for a Next-Generation Traffic Management System in the TANGENT project

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Abstract. This paper introduces the TANGENT project and how it is exploring Dynamic Management of Multimodal Traffic in four European cities. It focuses on how specific software patterns and architectural decisions are contributing to the success in creating and trialling a Simulation powered Next-Generation Traffic Management System. It starts by exploring the motivation behind a TANGENT API where a REST API coexists with a Message Queue Broker and how they synergize to cover the different needs of distinct data producers and consumers within and around the TANGENT project. It then explores a generic approach for the different pieces of the TANGENT API. How incoming data handling from the message queue service is implemented generically in the TANGENT API, how the REST API is implemented with this same approach and how the OpenAPI documentation of the REST API is produced. Highlighting the central role of the JSON Schemas and meta-data stored in TANGENT Schema catalogue and how it is simple to add new data sources with this approach as opposed to custom handling the individual data sources.

Keywords: Next-Generation Traffic Management System, Transport APIs, Multimodal Traffic Management.

1 Introduction

The TANGENT project [1] is exploring Dynamic Management of Multimodal Traffic in four European cities (Athens, Manchester, Lisbon and Rennes) by creating and trialling a Simulation powered Next-Generation Traffic Management System.

Data is a first-class citizen in the TANGENT project. It originates in data sources from a myriad of entities and services covering the four case study cities. In a first step, Service 0 (S0 in Fig. 1 below), is responsible for the collection, harmonisation and fusion of these data sources. It uses a Data Catalogue and an internal RDF-based Meta-model to achieve this. This Meta-model is based on transportation standards like Datex II [2], SIRI [3] and NeTEX [4]. It then outputs data in a JSON serialisation that is used by the TANGENT API in Service 1 (S1). All data elements sent from Service 0 to

Service 1 are JSON serialized, and each type of data element follows a JSON Schema that is directly derived from the RDF Meta-model.

TANGENT Services (S0-3), their data flows and the main data entities involved are depicted in Fig. 1 below.

Fig. 1. TANGENT Project Data flow diagram.

The TANGENT API from S1 is responsible for all internal and external project data exchange. This service also includes a User Interface component, denominated the TANGENT Dashboard. With the data originally coming from Service 0, the TANGENT Dashboard can provide multiple integrated visualisations, be it in maps, tables or KPI summary views. Services 2 and 3 complement the visualisation functionality with the ability to detect, analyse, plan, and implement responses to network disruptions and incidents in a multimodal, cooperative fashion. Response plans are prepared through the creation of templates that identify the detection conditions for network disruptions/incidents, characterize the incident and include a transport simulation model that can produce an optimised response plan for the given situation. A simulation engine runs the transport model for each template and produces optimisation results which are stored. When the Response Plan is activated due to degrading conditions on the network, the optimisation results in the template are presented to users in the Dashboard and cooperatively they will decide to change or directly apply the optimisation results to address the degraded conditions. These results can range from changes to Public Transport scheduling to changing traffic light plans and priorities, combining changes to several modes of transport in the city to produce an optimised response.

The TANGENT API is a central element in this project, exchanging data between the different Services. This includes both data coming originally from the cities as well as data supporting communication between the different Services to provide more advanced functionality, such as creating and implementing Response Plans. This central role is illustrated in the diagram of the TANGENT Tool architecture at Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. TANGENT Detailed Technical architecture.

2 Complementing REST and AMQP services

The entire TANGENT API is implemented both as REST services and, correspondingly, as messages in a Message Queue service (using AMQP). The message queue service provides real-time capabilities used by multiple services, including the User Interface. The REST services provide an OpenAPI documented interface where data can be fetched and delivered as needed. The messages exchanged follow the same JSON Schemas in both technologies. The JSON Schemas for the data coming from the cities are produced from the RDF Meta-model that is central to Service 0. The remaining JSON Schemas, namely those used for inter-service communication, are automatically produced from data samples in JSON and reviewed and enhanced manually.

Most Open data APIs for multi-modal transportation, and generally, Open data APIs, are implemented as REST services, offering queryable data sources in formats such as JSON, CSV and XML. The reason for this is probably because it's easier to implement user applications based on queryable data sources (as offered by REST services) instead of real-time messaging services (as offered by message queues).

A user application typically opens an entry screen with live information about a transport network / city and offers a set of planning functionalities, such as finding the best routes to a destination or determining the best time to leave work so you can arrive home or somewhere else before a certain time. This usage pattern fits well with queryable data sources, where the application can fetch live data and execute queries for the desired routing and other functionality as needed.

This rationale behind user applications was also part of the motivation behind offering the TANGENT API as a REST OpenAPI documented interface using only well-documented JSON payloads. This allows the TANGENT API to fit well with the existing Transport and Smart city API ecosystem and positions the TANGENT API as a

potential source of data for User Applications. The queryable data source pattern offered by the REST part of the TANGENT API also fits well with most of the needs of the TANGENT Dashboard, namely fetching the data to feed to live transport data widgets on a user's Dashboard.

But data displayed on the TANGENT Dashboard is not static. It typically changes periodically and it needs to be updated on the user interfaces. This is one use case where the REST services model shows its limitations. There are a few ways to overcome this limitation in REST APIs, namely Long pooling, Webhooks, Server-Sent Events or opting altogether for a different integration method such as Websockets. Most of these solutions involve setting up a dedicated permanent communication channel and, in some cases, involve exposing services from the client-side, which may be cumbersome and undesirable from the networking perspective.

The real-time update of data is not the only TANGENT Tool requirement not adequately covered by the REST API. A more advanced functionality such as Incident Management, involves the system monitoring a set of predefined conditions that will identify an occurring Incident, such as traffic occupancy or public transport occupancy surpassing a given threshold. It is crucial to evaluate these conditions as soon as the data behind them changes. Other such situations exist, namely having to generate calculated data and produce forecasts once new live information is available.

The fundamental technical limitation with the REST API that had to be overcome to adequately support all the previous use cases was the same, the lack of a real-time communication channel from the API towards its clients. This is where the Message Queue principle came into play. Unlike most ways used to overcome this limitation with REST APIs, message queues do not involve the need to setup a listening endpoint on the client side and decouple the connection between API producers and consumers / clients, allowing for a large number of distinct message producers and consumers.

Also, adopting a Message Queue to coexist with REST on the TANGENT API, allowed offering a native event driven solution alongside a queryable data solution, providing the TANGENT API clients with the best of both worlds.

Data is published directly to the Message Queue by distinct producers in Service 0 through to Service 3. It is persisted by a TANGENT API Service that subscribes to all known topics of the message queue, and that is how data becomes available for the REST API. Internal TANGENT API consumers will use the Message Queue primarily as they are either data producers, data transformers (subscribing to data that they enhance or use to produce up-to-date forecasts) or offer asynchronous services (such as optimising an incident response plan).

The TANGENT API REST component is used by the TANGENT Dashboard to fetch data to display in its widgets and by third-party applications that can benefit from TANGENT's harmonised data.

In terms of architecture quality, a pure solution would not include the overlapping functionality of AMQP and REST. It would be a cleaner approach to evolve to a purely Message Broker based solution. Still, we do not envision that to be the best solution for the TANGENT API because of the queryable data nature of the REST API which is more natural for many applications and due to the lack of formal documentation

mechanism in Message Queues, such as OpenAPI in REST APIs. Thus, we predict that, for the time-being, the duality of the TANGENT API will be an asset.

3 A Generic Data-Driven API

All the data flows coming from Service 0 to the TANGENT API involve indexing and storing the received data. TANGENT components that need to act on data once it becomes available, subscribe to the appropriate message queue topics. For instance, a triggering mechanism for the Response Plans, in Service 2, subscribes all the topics in the message queue for the data elements that it is monitoring. The event component of the architecture, based on the native events of the Message Queue, allows for a generic implementation of the main data processing services.

This motivated the development of generic approaches for incoming data handling from the message queue service in the TANGENT API, for the implementation of the REST API and for producing the OpenAPI documentation of the REST API from the JSON Schemas and meta-data stored in TANGENT.

This is not a new concept and has been promoted by works such as [5] and [6]. Handling data from different sub-domains is not an intrinsically distinct task. For TANGENT all data must be indexed and persisted; whatever actions need to be done, based on the data, can be defined through handlers for subscriptions to the message topic, namely updating the Dashboard or evaluating conditions regarding Incident detection.

The central element behind all generic approaches for the TANGENT API is the meta-data that lists all integrated data sources, identifying the message queue topics they arrive to, their REST base URL, their JSON schema, the database collections where the data should be stored, the permissions needed by users who can access each data source and several other specific aspects that provide distinguishing behaviour to the different data sources.

The service that handles incoming messages to the Message Queue simply has to listen to all the data source topics, indexing and persisting any received messages in the respective collection.

The REST API is a generic service that handles all request paths and validates them against the possible paths for the different data sources. Once matched, and access is validated, the respective action can be performed in a generic way, either read or store data.

The REST API is documented using the OpenAPI standard. Although the REST API implementation is generic, the OpenAPI documentation needs to include the signature of all the Data Requirements covered by the API. To this end, our solution uses the meta-data, where the URLs, JSON Schema, allowed operations, and parameters are defined to produce the OpenAPI documentation. JSON Schema objects will be converted into OpenAPI Schema Objects. The remaining elements of the OpenAPI Schema for each data source will be produced through Templates based on the remaining configuration elements present in the meta-data.

Instead of creating a custom API for each of the Data Sources supported in the TANGENT project, we opted for this generic solution. This allowed to systematically identify the common requirements of the data handling process, implement a generic solution covering these requirements and now it is straightforward to integrate new data sources without having to implement new code.

Our generic approach extended also into the Data Visualisation strategies, a topic which will be explored in future works.

4 Conclusions

As a Next Generation Traffic Management System, the TANGENT Tool will offer a multimodal view of urban transportation systems. It will also allow the cooperative management of network disruptions and incidents using optimised response plans obtained by simulations.

The composition of the TANGENT API as a combination of REST and a Message Queue allows dynamic choice between queryable data sources and event driven ones, delivering a robust and versatile integration platform for a wide spectrum of use cases.

Implementing the Tool through Generic API services allowed to focus on the data being exchanged and how it is displayed on the User Interface, instead of having to program the API specifically for each data source being handled. Adding new data sources became only a matter of configuration and testing.

Being generic, the API can also cater to new data source needs. It will capture these needs as configuration aspects and provide a generic solution to handle them, meaning it can be applied to other future data sources sharing the same need.

In the end, the ability to combine data from different modes of transport, the inclusion of forecasts and cooperatively implementing Response Plans based on simulation, overcome limitations of the vertical segmented systems operating transportation in most cities.

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